

RESEARCH ARTICLE ↓

Igbo Apprenticeship Practice and Mentorship of Young Entrepreneurs in Coal Camp Automobile Spare Parts Market, Enugu

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Abstract

This study examined Igbo apprenticeship practice and mentorship of young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu. The objectives of the study were to ascertain the degree of relationship between igba boi (servant apprenticeship) and providing business support to young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu, determine the degree of relationship between imu oru (learning craft or vocation) and intervening on behalf of mentees during and after the apprenticeship programme and evaluate the degree of relationship between imu ahia (learning trade) and exposing the apprentice to networking opportunities in the coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu. The descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study was 479 while the sample size of 218 was adopted using the Taro Yamane’s formula. The data were analysed using frequencies and percentages while the hypotheses were tested using the Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient. The findings included that there was significant degree of relationship between igba boi and providing business support to apprentice in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu. spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.7, there was significant degree of relationship between imu oru and intervening on behalf of the mentees during and after the apprenticeship programme in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu, spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.8 and there was significant degree of relationship between imu ahia and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu. Spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.9. This study concluded that Igbo apprenticeship practice has significant relationship with mentorship of young entrepreneurs, and it was recommended that the master should provide business support to the mentees, intervene on behalf of the mentees during and after the apprenticeship programme and also expose the mentees to networking opportunities in the automobile spare parts market.

Keywords: Igbo Apprenticeship Practice; Mentorship; Igba-boi (Servant Apprenticeship); Imu Oru (learning craft or vocation); Imu Ahia (Learning Trade)

Introduction

The civil war dislocated the Igbos from other parts of Nigeria to their Eastern Nigeria ancestral homeland which incidentally was the epicenter of the war (Umeadi, 2021). At the end of the war in 1970, most of them had lost their investments and businesses; not only were they not able to continue their pre-war position at the forefront of education, public administration, the military, industry or commerce; they found themselves outside the mainstream of all the economic sectors of the Nigerian economy and society. Also, due to lack of capital and near exclusion from the financial sector, they could not benefit from the indigenization policies of the 1970s that transferred ownership of many foreign owned businesses to Nigerians.

Based on this, Anyanwu (2019) observes that Igbo people no longer look up to benevolent government for salvation but are working towards self-reliance, and even contributes up to 80% of Nigeria's economy while receiving the lowest decreasing allocation from the federal government. Being excluded from most of the sectors of the economy and financially handicapped, petty trading became one of the few options open to them to make a living and it became a survival strategy for the Igbo people. They initiated an unwritten rule of 'zero tolerance' for youth and adult idleness and interestingly many of them flourished over time. Those who were able to restart their lives as traders and craftsmen took in more apprentices at a higher level than before the Nigerian Civil War. The system was mutually beneficial to the business person and to the apprentice. To business people, the motivation was a rational economic decision to use cheap labour for the augmentation of limited resources, while to the young people whose parents did not have the resources to send them to school, apprenticeship offered them sustenance, the opportunity to acquire new usable skills and the hope of becoming self-employed while reducing the financial burden on their families.

The Igbo culture of entrepreneurship can be traced back to the slave trade business from the 15th century. This process continued until the abolition of slave trade in the 1900s. Unlike most African communities, slaves from the Igbo ethnic group were exposed to entrepreneurship by their owners' trading commodities like sugar, spices, tobacco, and cotton for export to Europe and Asia and America. This action kindled the entrepreneurship spirit of the Igbo people and galvanized them to quickly venture into various forms of entrepreneurship during the pre-colonial era. The colonial era met the Igbos as the leading exporters of palm oil and kernel, craftsmen, traders, merchants, cottage industrialists, etcetera. This culture of entrepreneurship has been sustained till the present age through the apprenticeship framework (Wikipedia).

The Igbo Apprenticeship System is an unpaid business apprenticeship/incubator model that allows people learn business from a master for a certain number of years depending and at the end of their apprenticeship tenure, get cash infusion and support to start their own business. There is no salary paid during the time of the apprenticeship tenure but meals, clothing and fare are provided for by the master. When the years of learning are over, the boy is as good as his master.

Entrepreneurial development has helped in shaping the economy of most of the advanced and developed nations for over a century now. Igbo people view entrepreneurship as self-employment of any sort, which bothers on continuously identifying, evaluating and taking advantage of business opportunities and initiating sustainable action to ensure success. Indeed, every entrepreneurial endeavour, for the Igbo, is also a veritable answer to the questions elicited from their experiences in their special world. It is as well understood as a search for profit based on innovation, creativity and efficient utilization of resources in a consistent Igbo cultural pattern, which is filled with vision and enthusiasm and is result driven. Therefore, entrepreneurship for the Igbo people incorporates every profit and goal-oriented strategies which they describe as Ibidoahia or Oru (starting an enterprise), Izuahia (business transactions), Imu ahia (learning a trade), Imu oru (learning a craft or vocation), and Igbaosoahia (indulging in trick of marketing another's goods with his consent at a price that raises capital).

Statement of the Problem

Ideally, Igbo apprentice system is a rational economic decision that uses cheap labour to build up human resources, while creating the opportunity of developing self-employed individuals. It helps entrepreneur to know where to buy goods at a cheaper rate and how to sell them. Many families send their children to apprenticeship practice before providing capital for their own business. This helps them to master all the strategies and techniques of the particular business. They also use this method to change or diversify their businesses if their former businesses are not as profitable as they expected.

Unfortunately, dishonesty on the part of the Master or the apprentice has tended to dent the good intentions of the Igbo apprenticeship system. It has been observed that towards the expiration of the agreed apprenticeship period in some cases that Masters accuse the apprentices of frivolous crimes and send them away just to avoid their contractual obligations and thus deprive them of the settlement entitlements. Similarly, due to the fears of this scenario and sometimes due to inherent dishonesty, apprentices also run away with their Master's money or properties.

The consequences of not adopting the Igbo apprenticeship practices in entrepreneurship could lead to lack of intervention by mentees for young entrepreneurs. Furthermore, it could lead lack of exposure to networking opportunities for young entrepreneurs. Finally, it could lead to lack of business support by mentors. It is based on these that this study examined Igbo apprenticeship practice and mentorship of young entrepreneurs in Coal Camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu.

Objectives of the Study

1. Ascertain the degree of relationship between igba boi/odibo (servant apprenticeship) and providing business support for young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu.
2. Determine the level of relationship between imu oru (artisan/craft apprenticeship) and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu.
3. Evaluate the degree of relationship between imu ahia (trade apprenticeship) and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu.

Research Questions

1. What is the degree of relationship between igba boi and providing business support for young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu?
2. What is the degree relationship between imu oru and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu?
3. What is the degree of relationship between imu ahia and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu?

Statement of Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the following null hypotheses were formulated

1. There is no significant degree of relationship between igba boi and providing business support to young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu.
2. There is no significant relationship between imu oru and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu.
3. There is no significant relationship between imu ahia and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu.

Significance of the Study

This study will be beneficial to young entrepreneurs who are enrolled in Igbo apprenticeship practices, their masters and government.

Young Entrepreneurs: Young entrepreneurs will benefit from this study because through the findings of this study, they will be more enlightened about the prospects of the Igbo apprenticeship practice.

The Masters of the Young Entrepreneurs: The masters of the young entrepreneurs will benefit from this study because they will come to realize that the Igbo apprenticeship practice is a two way thing where the person who is on apprenticeship serves you for an agreed number of years and you are expected to settle the person.

Government: The government will benefit from this study because the study leads to economic development via reduction in the unemployment rate.

Scope of the Study

This study covered Igbo apprenticeship practice and mentorship of young entrepreneurs. The Igbo apprenticeship practices that were covered in this study include igba boi (servant apprenticeship), imu oru (learning craft or vocation) and imu ahia (learning trade) while the mentorship covered in this study include providing business support to young entrepreneurs, intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities. The geographical location of the study is Coal Camp Automobile Spare Parts Market, Enugu.

Limitations of the Study

The researcher came across diverse constraints in the course of carrying out this study. They include uncooperative attitude of the respondents and difficulty in accessing some of the respondents that form part of the study.

Uncooperative Attitude of the Respondents: Some of the apprentice respondents were complacent. They felt that the researcher might have been sent by their master to get some vital information from them but this challenge was subdued after much explanation by the researcher that the study was for academic purpose.

Difficulty in Accessing the Respondents: The researcher found it very difficult to access the respondents because most times the researcher came to their place of work, they were always very busy with one kind of work or the other. This challenge was subdued by encroaching on the time for their lunch and using that time to distribute the copies of questionnaire and also to collect them some days later.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Igbo Apprenticeship Practice

The Igbo apprentice system is an extension of their entrepreneurial make-up where a strategic training process is utilized to train mostly young men of igbo stock into entrepreneurial ventures by established entrepreneurs locally known as Oga, (Ejo-Orusa, 2019). This venture can be a trade, an enterprise or a vocation, in some cases serving also as a domestic help. The Ogas are former apprentices that had served and were settled with seed capitals to begin their own enterprises (Alike & Umunze, 2019). This system is informal and has unstructured training programs to learn and master skills required to embark on own enterprise. Basically, research has it that there are three ways of practicing apprenticeship in Igbo lands; these types are the Igba-Boy (serving)Imu-Ahia (learning trade) and imu oru (learning craft or vocation).

Today, Imu ahia, Igba boi and Imu oru have grown to become a cultural heritage in the Eastern region of Nigeria as it have been passed from generation to generation. The Igbo Apprenticeship system all started because the Igbo people needed to take back their future which was taken from them. Because they had barely to survive on and limited resources to use, they had to figure out a way of generating revenue at any time. Petty trade was one of the only ways to build back destroyed communities as well as farming, but then, farming required time that was not readily available at that moment.

Mentorship

Mentoring is a relationship between two individuals based on a mutual desire for development towards career goals and objectives. The relationship is a non-organizational structure in place. It is additional to other forms of assistance, such as developmental assignments, classroom instruction, on-the-job training, and coaching (Clutterbuck, 2019).

Hay (2019) posits that in a mentoring relationship the two individuals are referred to as the “mentor” and the “mentee” (the individual being mentored). Mentoring provides development opportunities for both partners. In mentoring, there is no reporting relationship between the mentor and the mentee (i.e., a manager would not mentor a direct report). Mentoring is not intended to replace the relationship between employees and their managers. Mentors do not conduct or provide input to performance reviews.

Entrepreneurs

Entrepreneurship is the manifest ability and willingness of individuals, on their own, in teams, within and outside existing organizations, to perceive and create new economic opportunities (new products, new production methods, new organizational schemes and new product-market combinations) and to introduce their ideas in the market, in the face of uncertainty and other obstacles, by making decisions on location, form and the use of resources and institutions (Wennekers and Thurik, 2019). Thus, entrepreneurs are calculated risk takers. People who go into business have no guarantee of making profit.

Theoretical Framework

Social Exchange Theory

This study is anchored on social exchange theory (SET), which Homans (1961) defined as the exchange of activity, tangible or intangible, and more or less rewarding or costly, between at least two parties. Cost was viewed primarily in terms of alternative activities or opportunities foregone by the actors involved. Social exchange theory (SET) is among the most influential conceptual paradigms for understanding workplace behavior. Although different views of social exchange have emerged, theorists agree that social exchange involves a series of interactions that generate obligations (Emerson, 1976). Within SET, these interactions are usually seen as interdependent and contingent on the actions of another person (Blau, 1964). SET also emphasizes that these interdependent transactions have the potential to generate high-quality relationships.

Achievement Theory

David C. McClelland's need for achievement theory served as the foundation for this study. This motivating postulation, which he examined in his book "The Achieving Society," is founded on the concepts of achievement, affiliation, and power. According to the theory, each person or organization is motivated by one of the three main factors. These motivators do not come naturally to humans; instead, they are acquired through associations and experiences gathered through time and space. According to the theory, achievers prefer to suggest answers to issues and achieve specific goals, whereas associates require affection and association more than anyone else.

Empirical Review

In line with the objectives of the study, the following empirical studies were reviewed.

Master/Apprentice Dishonesty and Empowerment of Young Entrepreneurs

In a study conducted by Ezeajughu (2021) on the effect of the master/apprentice dishonesty on empowerment of young entrepreneurs in Auto Spare parts in Nnewi market, a population of 1326 was studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection. The z-test statistical tool was used in the analysis and it was found that master/apprentice dishonesty has significant effect on empowerment of young entrepreneurs in auto spare parts in Nnewi market.

In a related study conducted by Okeke and Osang (2021) on the relationship between master/apprentice dishonesty and empowerment of young entrepreneurs in Main Market Onitsha, a population of 1534 people was studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in the analysis and it was found that master/apprentice dishonesty has significant relationship with empowerment of young entrepreneurs in main market Onitsha.

Furthermore, Ejo-Orusa (2021) carried out a study on the extent master/apprentice dishonesty affects the empowerment of young entrepreneurs in Ariaria market, in the study a population of 1378 people was studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used in the analysis and it was found that master/apprentice dishonesty affects empowerment of young entrepreneurs in Ariaria market to a large extent.

Adesola (2021) carried out a study in Lagos State on the effect of master/apprentice dishonesty on empowerment of young entrepreneurs in Idumota market. In the study a population of 1678 was studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection. The Chi-Square statistical tool was used in the analysis and it was found that master/apprentice dishonesty has significant effect on empowerment of young entrepreneurs in Lagos state.

Inadequate Legal Framework to Guide the System and Encouraging Capability of Young Entrepreneurs

Fajobi (2022) conducted a study in Lagos state on the relationship between inadequate legal framework to guide the system and encouraging capability of young entrepreneurs in Balogun market. In the study, a population of 1265 people were studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection. The Spearman rank order correlation coefficient was used in the analysis and it was found that inadequate legal framework to guide the system has significant relationship with encouraging capability of young entrepreneurs.

In a related study conducted by Amusa (2022) in Kano state on the effect of inadequate legal framework to guide the system on encouraging capability of young entrepreneurs, in the study a population of 1236 people was studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection. The regression method of analysis was used in the analysis and it was found that inadequate legal framework to guide the system has significant effect on encouraging capability of young entrepreneurs in Kano State.

Prospect of Knowledge of the Strategies/techniques of business and Guidance provided by Mentors of Young Entrepreneurs

In a study conducted by Umeayo (2022) on the relationship between prospect of knowledge of the strategies of business and guidance provided by mentors of young entrepreneurs in Onitsha Main market, in the study a population of 1875 people were studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the instrument of data collection. The PPMC coefficient was used in the analysis and it was found that prospect of knowledge of the techniques of business and guidance provided by mentors of young entrepreneurs.

Onwuteka (2022) carried out a study in Enugu State on the effect of prospect of knowledge of the strategies of business on the guidance provided by mentors of young entrepreneurs. In the study a population of 1176 people were studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection and

it was found that prospect of knowledge of the strategies of business has significant effect on guidance provided by mentors of young entrepreneurs.

Gap in the Literature Review

Many studies have been conducted on Igbo apprenticeship practice and mentorship of young entrepreneurs but there is lack of literature on the variables used in this study: providing business support, intervening on behalf of the mentee and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities. Furthermore, there is a lack of literature on conducting the study in the Coal Camp Automobile Spare Parts Market, Enugu. Hence, the study covered the gap.

Methodology

Research Design

This descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. Research design deals with the strategy for identifying the problem, the data collection method, the data processing and interpretation of a study (Udeze, 2005). The justification for adopting the survey research design was because it scientifically explicates phenomena and their relationships in an actual environment with a specified time. The survey research design depends on sample of respondents drawn from the population and a considered representative of the population Also, Survey was also adopted in this research because the method was considered adequate and most appropriate in that it helped the researcher to describe, examine, record, analyze and interpret the variable that exists in the study to draw conclusions.

Area of the Study

The study was carried out at the Coal Camp Automobile Spare Parts Market, Enugu, Enugu State.

Sources of Data

Data for this study were gotten from the primary and secondary sources of data. The primary source constituted both the masters and apprentices at the automobile centre at Coal Camp making use of questionnaire while the secondary sources of data were those sources of data, which were not the original material of the researcher. They include textbooks, journals, internet materials, seminar etc. mainly from the different libraries in Enugu state.

Population of the Study

Kinnear and Taylor (1983) described population as the total of all elements defined prior to the reflection of a sample. The researcher studied all the Masters and Apprentices at the Coal Camp Automobile Spare Parts Market. The breakdown of the population is as follows:

Table 1: Distribution of the Population

<i>S/NO</i>	<i>Coal Camp Automobile Centre</i>	<i>Number of workers</i>
1	Masters (Oga)	108
2	Apprentice (Nwa Boi)	371
	Total	479

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Therefore, the population of the study is 479.

Determination of Sample Size

The Taro Yamane's formula was used to determine the sample size. The formula is stated thus;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad \text{Where } n = \text{sample size, } N = \text{population of the study, } 1 = \text{Mathematical constant}$$

e = error limit. In this study, the population of the study is 479. The error limit is 5% i.e. 0.05 Substituting in the above formula, we have

$$= \frac{479}{1+479(0.05)^2} = \frac{479}{1+479 \times 0.0025} = \frac{479}{1+1.185} = \frac{479}{2.1975} = 217.97$$

Approximately = 218, therefore, sample size = 218

Using the Bowley's formula, the stratified sample size was determined.

$$\text{For Masters (Oga), } n = \frac{218 \times 108}{479} = 49.15 \text{ Approximately equal to } 49$$

$$\text{For Apprentice (Nwa Boi), } n = \frac{218 \times 371}{479} = 168.8 = 169$$

Sampling Technique

The study adopted the simple random sampling technique. In the simple random sampling technique, the researcher randomly selected the respondents and could not influence the choice of those selected.

Instruments of Data Collection

The researcher collected data through the use of structured questionnaire making use of five-point likert scale of strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree. This was conducted with the help of a research assistant and after a day interval, the researcher with the help of the assistant collected the copies of questionnaire.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument for data collection was both face and content validated. This was carried out by giving some copies of questionnaire to the supervisor, other senior lecturers in the faculty who are quite knowledgeable in questionnaire drafting to criticize and comment on the structure and content. The corrections made by the experts were duly reflected in the final draft of the questionnaire.

Reliability of the Instrument

Reliability of the questionnaire was ascertained by giving 20 copies of questionnaire to some respondents to answer. After an interval of two days, the same instrument was administered a second time on the same group of people. The first and second responses were collated and analyzed through the application of Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient. The result of the analysis showed an average of 0.81 percent consistent and could be relied upon.

Method of Data Analysis

The data analysis method consists of descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequency tables and mean were used while the inferential statistics using the z-test statistics was used to test the hypothesis.

Results

Data Presentation

Distribution and Return of Questionnaire:

Table 2: Distribution and Return of Questionnaire

<i>Cadre</i>	<i>Number of Questionnaire Distributed</i>	<i>Number of Questionnaire Returned</i>	<i>Number of Questionnaire Lost</i>	<i>% of Valid Questionnaire</i>
<i>Master</i>	49	42	7	19
<i>Apprentice</i>	169	154	15	71
Total	218	196	22	90

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 2 shows that out of 49 copies of questionnaire distributed to the Masters at Coal Camp Automobile Spare Parts Market, 7 copies were lost, while 42 copies representing 19% of the total copies were returned. Out of a total of 169 copies of questionnaire distributed to the apprentice, 15 copies were lost while 154 copies representing 71% of the total copies were returned. Therefore, the total number of valid questionnaires is 196 copies representing 90% of the total copies of questionnaire distributed.

Data Relating to Research Questions

What is the degree of relationship between igba boi and providing business support to young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu?

Table 3: Mean rating of the relationship between igba boi and providing business support to young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu

S/N	ITEMS	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	Mean
1	Apprentices are adequately settled by masters after serving out the agreed period of apprenticeship	56 (28%)	68 (35%)	25 (13%)	27 (14%)	20 (10%)	196	3.57
2	Master provides apprentice with a shop in addition to cash settlement	64 (35%)	60 (28%)	22 (19%)	26 (10%)	24 (8%)	196	3.58
3	Apprentice are provided with tools to start up	68 (36%)	59 (27%)	23 (24%)	26 (7%)	20 (6%)	196	3.65

Grand Mean of Table = 3.61

Table 3 shows that 56 respondents strongly agree that apprentice is adequately settled by masters after serving out the agreed period of apprenticeship at coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu, 68 respondents agree, 25 respondents were undecided, 27 respondents disagree while 18 respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.57

Table 3 shows that 64 respondents strongly agree that master provides apprentice with a shop in addition to cash settlement, 60 respondents agree, 22 respondents were undecided, 26 respondents disagree while 23 respondents strongly disagree with a mean of 3.58

Table 3 shows that 68 respondents strongly agree that apprentices are provided with tools to start up, 59 respondents agreed, 23 respondents were undecided, 26 respondents disagreed while 20 respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.65. The grand mean of table is 3.60

What is the relationship between imu oru and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile sector in Enugu metropolis?

Table 4: Mean rating of the relationship between imu oru and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs at coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu

S/N	ITEMS	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	Mean
1	Master provides proper guide to apprentice during apprenticeship	53 (27%)	66 (34%)	23 (12%)	32 (16%)	22 (11%)	196	3.48
2	Master defends apprentice during and after apprenticeship	69 (35%)	61 (31%)	24 (12%)	23 (12%)	19 (10%)	196	3.70
3	Master partners and refers customers to apprentice after apprenticeship	63 (32%)	57 (29%)	28 (14%)	27 (14%)	21 (11%)	196	3.54

Grand Mean of Table = 3.58

Table 4 shows that 53 respondents strongly agree that master provides proper guide to apprentice during apprenticeship in coal camp automobile spare parts market, 66 respondents agree, 23 respondents were undecided, 32 respondents disagree while 22 respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.48

Table 4 shows that 69 respondents strongly agree that the Master defends apprentice during and after apprenticeship at coal camp automobile spare parts market, 61 respondents agree, 24 respondents were undecided, 23 respondents disagree while 19 respondents strongly disagree with a mean of 3.70.

Table 4 shows that 63 respondents strongly agree that master partners and refers customers to apprentice after apprenticeship at coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu. 57 respondents agreed, 28 respondents were undecided, 27 respondents disagreed while 21 respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.54

What is the relationship between imu ahia and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu?

Table 5: Mean rating of the relationship between imu ahia and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu

S/N	ITEMS	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	Mean
1	Mentors teach mentees market strategies	54 (27%)	66 (34%)	27 (12%)	28 (16%)	21 (11%)	195	3.53
2	Mentors show mentees where to buy goods at cheaper rate	70 (35%)	57 (29%)	23 (12%)	24 (12%)	23 (12%)	195	3.67
3	Mentors connect apprentice to business partners and opportunities	69 (35%)	59 (30%)	31 (16%)	25 (13%)	12 (6%)	195	3.76

Grand Mean of Table = 3.66

Table 5 shows that 54 respondents strongly agree that mentors teach mentees business strategies in coal camp automobile spare parts market is high probability of success in business, 27 respondents were undecided, 28 respondents disagree while 21 respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.52.

Table 5 shows that 70 respondents strongly agree that mentors provides the mentees knowledge of where to buy goods at cheaper rate, 57 respondents agree, 23 respondents were undecided, 24 respondents disagree while 23 respondents strongly disagree with a mean of 3.66.

Table 5 shows that 62 respondents strongly agree that mentors connect apprentice to business partners and opportunities, 59 respondents agreed, 31 respondents were undecided, 25 respondents disagreed while 12 respondents strongly disagreed with a mean of 3.74

Test of Hypotheses

This section dealt essentially with statistical testing of the hypotheses formulated for this study and also interpreting the result by adopting the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient.

Test of Hypothesis One

Ho: There is no significant degree of relationship between igba boi and providing business support to young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu

Table 6: Spearman Rank Correlation between igba boi and providing business support to young entrepreneurs

Variable	Data 1	Data 2	Rank 1	Rank 2	D	D ²
A	56	64	4	5	1	1
B	68	60	5	4	1	1
C	25	22	2	1	1	1
D	27	26	3	3	0	0
E	20	24	1	2	1	1
						$\sum D^2 = 4$

Calculating the Spearman Rank: Correlation coefficient of the ranked data

$$R = 1 - (6 \sum d^2) / n(n^2 - 1).$$

Analysis of the Result: Spearman rank correlative (calculated) = 0.7

Spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.7 Calculating the Spearman rank correlation coefficient of the ranked data= $R = 1 - (6 \sum d^2) / n(n^2 - 1).$

Analysis of the Result:

Spearman rank correlation (calculated) = 0.7 Spearman rank (table) at $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.7. The first hypothesis states that there is no significant degree of relationship between igba boi and providing business support for young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu. The calculated spearman rank correlation (0.7) is greater than the table spearman rank correlation (0.05). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is significant degree of relationship between igba boi and providing business support to young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho: There is no significant relationship between imu oru and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu.

Table 7: Spearman Rank Correlation between imu oru and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs

Variable	Data 1	Data 2	Rank 1	Rank 2	D	D ²
A	53	69	4	5	1	1
B	66	61	5	4	1	1
C	23	24	2	3	1	1
D	32	23	3	2	1	1
E	22	19	1	1	0	0
						$\sum D^2 = 4$

Calculating the Spearman Rank: Correlation coefficient of the ranked data

$$R = 1 - (6 \sum d^2) / n(n^2 - 1)$$

Analysis of the Result: Spearman rank correlative (calculated) = 0.8

Spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.8 Calculating the Spearman rank correlation coefficient of the ranked data= $R = 1 - (6 \sum d^2) / n(n^2 - 1)$

Analysis of the Result:

Spearman rank correlation (calculated) = 0.8 Spearman rank (table) at $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.8

The second hypothesis states that there is significant relationship between imu oru and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs. The calculated spearman rank correlation (0.8) is greater than the table spearman rank correlation (0.05). Therefore the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there exist significant positive relationship between imu oru and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho: There is no significant relationship between imu ahia and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities in coal camp automobile spare parts market, Enugu.

Table 8: Spearman Rank Correlation between imu ahia and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities

Variable	Data 1	Data 2	Rank 1	Rank 2	D	D ²
A	54	70	4	5	1	1
B	66	57	5	4	1	1
C	27	23	2	3	1	1
D	28	24	3	1	2	4
E	21	23	1	2	0	0
						$\sum D^2 = 7$

Calculating the Spearman Rank: Correlation coefficient of the ranked data

$$R = 1 - (6\sum d^2) / n(n^2-1)$$

Analysis of the Result: Spearman rank correlative (calculated) = 0.9

Spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.9 Calculating the Spearman rank correlation coefficient of the ranked data= $R = 1 - (6\sum d^2) / n(n^2-1)$.

Analysis of the Result:

Spearman rank correlation (calculated) = 0.9 Spearman rank (table) at $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.9

The second hypothesis states that there is significant relationship between imu ahia and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities. The calculated spearman rank correlation (0.9) is greater than the table spearman rank correlation (0.05). Therefore the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there exist significant positive relationship between imu oru and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities.

Discussion of Findings

Discussion based on Hypothesis One

There is significant degree of relationship between igba boi and providing business support to young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu. The evidence is shown in the spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.7. In the empirical review conducted by Okeke & Osang (2022) on the relationship between dishonesty of the master/apprentice and empowering young entrepreneurs, although the research and that of the researcher were conducted using different analytical method and different locations, it was found there is significant degree of relationship between dishonesty of the master/apprentice and empowering young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile centre in Enugu metropolis

Discussion based on Hypothesis Two

There is significant degree of relationship between imu oru and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu. The evidence is shown in the spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.8. In the empirical review conducted by Fajobi (2022) on the relationship between inadequate legal framework and encouraging capability of young entrepreneurs and it was discovered that there is significant relationship between in adequate legal framework to guide the system and encouraging capability of young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile sector in Enugu metropolis.

Discussion based on Hypothesis Three

There is significant degree of relationship between imu ahia and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu. The evidence is shown in the spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.8. In the empirical review conducted by Umeayo (2022) on the relationship between

prospect of knowledge of the techniques of business and guidance provided by the mentor and it was discovered that there is significant relationship between the prospect of knowledge of the strategies/techniques of business and guidance provided by mentors of young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile sector in Enugu metropolis.

Summary of Findings

1. There is significant degree of relationship between igba boi and providing business support to young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.7
2. There is significant relationship between imu oru and intervening on behalf of young entrepreneurs in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.8
3. There is significant relationship between imu ahia and exposing young entrepreneurs to networking opportunities in coal camp automobile spare parts market Enugu. Spearman rank (table) $p = 0.05$ is less than 0.9

Conclusion

Apprenticeship scheme in Igboland, South Eastern Nigeria, has generated a great deal of interest. The study identified mentoring as a tool that could be adopted in transforming the Igbos who are naturally enterprising and creative to adequately have attitudinal change in order to assist in repositioning the Sub-Saharan Africa in its competitiveness in global economy. Igbo apprenticeship practices should be encouraged and the apprentices should be well mentored to be able to be good entrepreneurs.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. There should be adequate settlement and business support by the masters for the apprentices who served out his agree period of apprenticeship
2. There should be proper intervention by the masters on behalf of the apprentice during and after apprenticeship.
3. The master should be properly expose to apprentice to networking opportunities.

Contribution to Knowledge

The study made some contributions to knowledge. This included:

1. **Design:** The researcher adopted the survey research method on the subject matter unlike other researchers that used Ex-post Facto research method and experimental research method.
2. **Analytical Tool:** The researcher adopted the z-test statistical tool in the analysis. Other researchers that have carried out similar studies used the chi-square and Pearson product moment correlation.

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